

AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA USE ON ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AMONG UNDERGRADUATE BUSINESS STUDENTS (MADURAI KAMARAJ UNIVERSITY) IN TAMIL NADU

A. Rohini Priyadharsana

Part- Time Research Scholar, Department of Business Administration,
Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai – 625021

Dr. M.Sivakumar

Research Supervisor & Professor, Department of Entrepreneurship Studies,
School Business Studies, Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai - 625021

Abstract:

This study analyzes the impact of social media on the entrepreneurial aspirations of undergraduate business students in Tamil Nadu. Ellison's model of entrepreneurial intention was integrated with Shapero and Sokol's framework to assess entrepreneurial intention using the theory of planned behavior. The study's questionnaire underwent a validation process before being distributed for administration. The study's positive findings suggest that social media impacts students' views on operational feasibility, with only a limited impact on perceptions of attractive feasibility. Such significant discoveries have the potential to provide valuable insights for policymakers and educators in the field of entrepreneurship. This includes strategies for utilizing cutting-edge media and internet tools to foster entrepreneurial skills among the youth.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Intention, Social Media, Desirability, Feasibility, Business Students.

Introduction

Eco-development is now emphasized through the utilization of entrepreneurship and a strong entrepreneurial focus. Governmental and educational institutions have been dedicated to nurturing entrepreneurship in young individuals and aspiring entrepreneurs, in order to inspire them to pursue business ventures. Recent research has examined the motivations behind utilizing social networks and social media platforms like Facebook as a launching pad for entrepreneurial ventures. According to Kaplan et al., social networking sites, or social media, are web applications that facilitate the creation, modification, and sharing of user-generated content to facilitate interaction. Moreover, social media practices, such as those on workplace platforms and Google social networking sites, have emerged as integral activities in today's society (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010) and have had an impact on the standards and behaviors in both business and personal life (Hennig-Thurau et al, 2010). Within the current landscape of social networking platforms, there is a notable presence of active business marketing and promotion. This trend has led to a rise in the use of social media, raising questions about its impact on entrepreneurial intentions among younger individuals, as well as awareness of its potential capabilities. Bryer

elaborates on this concept by conceptualizing social networking websites as Business Operating Systems that serve as integrated platforms within the business environment, facilitating significant overhauls and the establishment of new ventures.

Despite existing research on the impacts of the Internet on entrepreneurs, there remains a gap in understanding how technologies and social media specifically influence individuals' intentions to start a business. This study aims to assess the impact of social network site usage on business intent among Tamil Nadu business students. It aims to offer insights into entrepreneurial intention and the factors influencing entrepreneurial decision-making in the context of new venture establishment. This study utilizes Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) to analyze the factors impacting entrepreneurial intention, also referred to as entrepreneurship intention variables. The study utilizes Information Technology (IT) acceptance theories including the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM1) (Davis et al., 1989), TAM2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003) to analyze the factors impacting responses in the prognostic model discussed. Data was collected through a quantitative survey of undergraduate business students at a group of colleges located in Tamil Nadu in the Southern region. The results of the hypothesis testing supported Ajzen's (1991) model of entrepreneurial intention and previous research. However, the impact of social networking site usage on perceived desirability and feasibility only partially confirmed the model, indicating potential for further research utilizing alternative sampling and methodology. The remaining sections of this paper cover the theoretical framework, methodology, results, discussion, implications, and conclusion.

Review of Literature:

There exists a plethora of academic literature discussing students' intentions, as numerous scholars have examined this subject in previous studies. Bird (1988) defines intentionality as a mental state that influences a person's motivation to achieve their goals. Internal cognition guides the individual's behavior by focusing attention. This perspective stays within the realm of thought, and individuals endorse it through self-dialogue. As mentioned in earlier literature, there has been inconsistent definition of entrepreneurship intention or its measurement in previous research by Sweida and Reichard (2013). It is important to recognize that intention comes before behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Perceived behavioral control is considered a more suitable predictor of intention than attitude, as suggested by Bagozzi et al. (1989) and Bagozzi (1981). Regarding this matter, the observation of intention shifts the focus from attitudes, beliefs, personality, demographics, and properties to the anticipated behavior (Krueger et al., 2000).

The literature on entrepreneurship has shown interest in the concept of entrepreneurship intention since the early 1980s. Shapero and Sokol (1982) introduced the Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM), one of the most well-known intention models in the field. Furthermore, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) was formulated by Ajzen (1991) to elucidate the concept of intention. The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) posits three predictors of intention: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control (Ajzen 1991; Ridha and Wahyu 2017; Soomro and Shah 2015). Moreover, according to the 1982 Shapero and Sokol model,

entrepreneurial intentions are influenced by the likelihood to act, perceived feasibility, and perceived desirability (Dabic et al., 2012; Urban and Kujinga, 2017). Perceived feasibility is analogous to perceived behavioral control, whereas perceived desirability aligns with attitude towards the act in Shapero and Sokol's (1982) model and Ajzen's (1991) model (Dabic et al., 2012; Krueger and Brazeal, 1994). **Social Media and Entrepreneurial Intention**

The significant rise in social media popularity and its widespread daily use among young people prompt the following hypothesis. These websites empower users by offering a range of choices and facilitating the acquisition of knowledge, resources, and social capital through online connections that would otherwise be inaccessible (Aldrich, Martinez, 2001; Burt, 2000; Hansen, 1995; Kirakosyan, 2014). The adoption of Social Media by new entrepreneurs can be influenced by a variety of factors that may or may not indicate an intention to pursue entrepreneurship. The current literature on entrepreneurship demonstrates a lack of research specifically focusing on Social Media entrepreneurship. Nevertheless, the impact of STS adoption on entrepreneurship intention could be assessed by validating the concepts and theories found in the IT adoption literature. Building upon the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis et al. (1989), this study explores the entrepreneurial intention to utilize social media and the key factors that impact such intentions. Specifically, this research focuses on five critical factors that play a significant role in influencing an entrepreneur's intention to adopt social media. The factors that are considered to have the most impact on determining the level of entrepreneurial intention towards using social media as a business platform for entrepreneurial operations include the perceived competitive usefulness (Heinrichs et al., 2011; Hughes, 2016), perceived ease of use (Ariff et al., 2014; Hughes, 2016; George et al., 2014; Venkatesh and Bala, 2008), and perceived competitive pressure (Hughes, 2016; Thong and Yap).

Research Objectives:

This study aims to contribute to the body of knowledge related to the intention of entrepreneurial individuals and the impact of social media on their intentions to carry out entrepreneurial activities. Thus, the study investigates the impact of social media on entrepreneurial intention among undergraduate business students in the Tamil Nadu context.

1. To understand the usage of social media which impacts undergraduate business students on entrepreneurial intentions.
2. To observe undergraduate business students, appreciate the usefulness of social media for entrepreneurial activities.
3. To validate the negative perceptions about social media hindering undergraduate business students' entrepreneurial intentions to start new businesses.
4. To observe the significance of the factors, that influence undergraduate business students' entrepreneurial intentions to employ social media in their entrepreneurial activities.

Research Framework

The Shapero and Sokol framework, also referred to as the Entrepreneurial Event Model (EEM), was created in 1982 to elucidate the determinants of entrepreneurial intentions. This model suggests that entrepreneurial intentions are influenced by three main factors: perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and propensity to act.

Key Components of the Model

Perceived Desirability: The attractiveness of initiating a business, influenced by an individual's positive or negative attitudes towards entrepreneurship.

Perceived Feasibility: An individual's evaluation of their capability to effectively start and operate a business, including their skills, resources, and opportunities.

Propensity to Act: The willingness of an individual to take steps towards starting a business, indicating their inclination and preparedness to participate in entrepreneurial endeavors.

These elements combine to shape an individual's intention to pursue entrepreneurship. The model underscores the necessity of a combination of factors for an entrepreneurial event to take place, including a credible opportunity that spurs action.

Research Methodology:

There is a lack of research on how the Internet and social media impact individuals' intentions to start a business, despite advancements in understanding its positive and negative effects on potential entrepreneurs. This study aims to assess the impact of social network site utilization on business intent among business students in Tamil Nadu. The purpose is to gain insights into entrepreneurial intention and the factors influencing entrepreneurial decision-making in the setting of new venture establishment. This study utilizes Ajzen's (1991) Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) as a theoretical framework to examine the determinants of entrepreneurial intention, also known as entrepreneurship intention factors. The study utilizes Information

Technology (IT) acceptance theories, including the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM1) (Davis et al., 1989), TAM2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh et al., 2003), to examine the factors influencing responses in the prognostic model outlined in this study. Data was collected through a quantitative survey of undergraduate business students attending a group of universities in Tamil Nadu, located in the southern region. The results of the hypothesis testing supported Ajzen's (1991) model of entrepreneurial intention and previous research. However, with regards to the impact of social networking site usage on perceived desirability and feasibility, it can be concluded that the model is only partially validated. This indicates potential for further research on the underlying dynamics of this relationship using a different sample.

Proposed Framework

Hypothesis:

H1. Perceived desirability has a positive effect on entrepreneurial intentions.

H2. Perceived feasibility has a positive effect on entrepreneurial intention.

H3: Social Media usage has a significant effect on perceived desirability.

H3a: Perceived ease of use of social media has a significant effect on perceived desirability.

H3b: The perceived privacy risk of social media has a significant effect on perceived desirability.

H4: Social Media usage has a significant effect on perceived feasibility.

H4a: Perceived ease of use of social media has a significant effect on perceived feasibility.

H4b: Perceived privacy risk of social media has a significant effect on perceived feasibility.

Analysis & Interpretation

The survey instrument was created using established entrepreneurial intention surveys that have undergone validation and assessment in prior studies. The tool comprises four segments that pertain to intention and use of social media. Validation procedures were utilized to assess both the instrument and the scales. Initially, four autonomous expert colleagues assessed the

questionnaire. Next, the validation phase entailed conducting a pilot survey with a sample size of 20 students. Subsequently, the data collected was thoroughly cleaned and analyzed. In addition, certain questions were rephrased to ensure clarity. Next, Cronbach's alpha and exploratory factor analysis were performed to assess the internal consistency of the questionnaire. Consequently, the list underwent screening, and the questions were reduced through standard validity and reliability testing. The 31 remaining items were used as the foundation of the questionnaire for the primary survey. A second validation phase of the survey data was completed through the utilization of Cronbach's α and confirmatory factor analysis. The outcome of the validation tests was correlated with the initial pilot test, resulting in a correlation value of 0.845. Hence, a five-point scale was utilized to enhance the validity of measuring participants' entrepreneurial intention in this research. The study's sample comprised students from Tamil Nadu. Lüthje and Franke (2003) recommend that emphasis be directed towards understanding the factors influencing students' entrepreneurial intentions. They argue that valuable insights can be gained from current students aspiring to pursue entrepreneurial careers, as opposed to graduates who have already established their businesses. Data on the opinions of university students regarding entrepreneurship could potentially promote and nurture an entrepreneurial mindset among undergraduates. The population comprised undergraduate business students at Madurai Kamaraj University in the Southern province. Participants were selected at random based on their respective proportions at the colleges in Tamil Nadu. The participants were students from a variety of disciplines, such as business administration, information systems, financial management, accounting, and marketing. Researchers initially ensured that all participants were briefed on the survey's main topic and purpose, emphasizing the voluntary nature of their participation and the confidentiality of their responses. Later, hard copies of the survey were disseminated to the participants along with brief instructions on how to properly fill it out. Ultimately, a total of 772 questionnaires were collected, of which 754 were deemed valid. A total of 18 questionnaires were disqualified for containing incomplete information. The data was examined through the utilization of SPSS and AMOS software. The respondent's descriptive analysis and information are displayed in Table 1

Table 1.0			
STATISTICS DESCRIPTIVE			
Characteristics	Total Sample	Male	Female
Sex	754	317	437
(%)	100	42.04	57.95
Between 22 and less than 30	36.50%	46.50%	26.90%
How long have you been using social media? (%)	Total Sample	Male	Female
Less than 6 months	0.80%	1.10%	0.60%

Between 6 months and less than 1 year	0.80%	0.80%	0.80%
Between 1 year and less than 3 year	6.00%	6.60%	5.40%
More than 3 year	92.40%	91.50%	93.20%
Time spent daily on Social Media (%)	Total Sample	Male	Female
Less than 3 hours	11.5	16.5	9.6
Between 3 hours and less than 6 hours	42.9	42.2	41.5
Between 6 hours and less than 9 hours	18.1	26.3	29.5
More than 9 hours	27.5	15	19.4
Number of contacts/friends having on social media?	Total Sample	Male	Female
Less than 100 friends	20.8	26	34.4
Between 100 friends and less than 300 friends	21.2	27.5	34
Between 300 friends and less than 500 friends	26.7	16.2	17.1
Between 500 friends and less than 1000 friends	20.6	13.5	8.4
More than 1000 friends	10.7	16.8	6.1
Do you accept strangers who try to friend you in social media?	Total Sample	Male	Female
Yes	35.2	19.4	12.0
No	11.4	24.7	36.5
Sometimes	53.4	56	51.5

Table 1 illustrates that the sample consisted of 327 male (43.4%) and 427 female (56.6%) participants. In terms of age, roughly 65% of the students fell within the 18 to 21 age range. The remaining students were aged between 22 and 30. A section of the questionnaire focused on Social Media usage. When asked about the duration of their Social Media engagement, the majority reported using it for over three years (93%). Furthermore, the study analyzed the daily time respondents dedicated to social media. It revealed that approximately 42% spent between three to six hours each day on these platforms, with around 30% specifically devoting between 3 to 6 hours daily to social media

Table 2						
REASONS OF USING SOCIAL MEDIA						
The reasons for using social media	Total		Male		Female	
	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Searching for information (%)	66.3	33.7	70.5	29.5	85.7	14.3
Playing e-games (%)	25	75	22	78	27.5	73.4
Forming professional relationships with the business environment (%)	35.9	64.1	25.2	74.8	72.7	27.3
Communicating with family and friends (%)	54.4	45.6	57.5	42.5	87.5	12.5
Making new friends (%)	21.1	78.9	45.6	54.4	37.7	62.3
Getting feedback (%)	15.5	84.5	38.5	61.5	33.3	66.7
Posting videos, photos ...etc (%)	37.7	62.3	36.7	63.3	38.4	61.6
Sharing my experience (%)	18.3	81.7	16.2	83.8	19.9	80.1

"Table 2 illustrates the students' responses such as 66.3% uses the social media for searching for information and 33.7 % students doesn't use it for searching for information. 25 % of the respondents uses for Playing e-games and 75 % of the respondents were not interested in Playing e-games. 35 % of respondents uses it for Forming professional relationships with the business environment, however 64.1 % of respondents are not interested in Forming professional relationships with the business environment. 54.4 % are using it for Communicating with family and friends and 45.6 % are not using for Communicating with family and friends.

Table 3.0**ACCESS TO SOCIAL MEDIA**

How often do you access your business and/or social media?	Total				
	Never	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	Hourly
Twitter	10.7	9.9	20.8	39.8	18.7
Facebook	79.6	12.6	5.6	2	0.3
YouTube	2.9	5.3	23.2	59.5	9
Google+	44	12.2	13.8	26.3	3.7
LinkedIn	90.2	5.4	2.1	1.3	0.9
Snapchat	17.8	1.7	3.4	35.3	41.8
Instagram	7.6	4.8	13.5	49.2	24.7
Salesforce Chatter	98.4	0.9	0.1	0.4	0.1
Skype	87.7	10.1	1.7	0.4	0.1
MySpace	99.3	0.5	0.1	0	0
path	91.2	1.6	0.8	3.1	3.3
Digg	99.2	0.5	0.1	0.1	0
Flickr	97.9	1.5	0.5	0.1	0
Reddit	97.1	2	0.5	0.4	0
Tumblr	97.1	0.4	0.5	1.5	0.5

Table 3.1					
ACCESS TO SOCIAL MEDIA					
	Male				
How often do you access your business and/or social media accounts	Never	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	Hourly
Twitter	10.1	8.3	17.4	42.2	22
Facebook	70.3	19.3	8	2.1	0.3
YouTube	1.5	4.3	18.3	63.3	12.5
Google+	44.3	15.3	15.6	21.4	3.4
LinkedIn	91.4	5.8	1.8	0.3	0.6
Snapchat	3.1	2.4	4.3	34.9	55.4
Instagram	5.8	6.1	15	44	28.7
Salesforce Chatter	99.1	0.6	0.3	0	0
Skype	82.6	14.7	1.8	0.6	0.3
MySpace	99.1	0.6	0.3	0	0
path	90.2	0.9	0.3	2.4	6.1
Digg	98.8	0.6	0.3	0.3	0
Flickr	96.9	1.5	1.2	0.3	0
Reddit	95.1	3.1	0.9	0.9	0
Tumblr	98.8	0.3	0.3	0.6	0

Table 3.2					
ACCESS TO SOCIAL MEDIA					
	Female				
How often do you access your business and/or social networking accounts	Never	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	Hourly
Twitter	11.2	11.2	23.4	37.9	16.2
Facebook	86.7	7.5	3.7	1.9	0.2
YouTube	4	6.1	26.9	56.7	6.3
Google+	43.8	9.8	12.4	30	4
LinkedIn	89.2	5.2	2.3	2.1	1.2
Snapchat	29	1.2	2.8	35.6	31.4
Instagram	8.9	3.7	12.4	53.2	21.5
Salesforce Chatter	97.9	1.2	0.7	0.2	0
Skype	91.6	6.6	1.6	0.2	0
MySpace	99.5	0.5	0	0	0

Tables 3.0 to 3.2 highlight the most favored social media platforms among business school students in Tamil Nadu. The analysis reveals that Snapchat, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter rank as the most frequently used platforms, with notable gender differences: males tend to favor YouTube, while females are more inclined towards Snapchat. In contrast, sites like MySpace, Digg, Salesforce Chatter, Flickr, Reddit, and Templer showed minimal usage among the surveyed participants.

As previously indicated in Table 2 and further supported by Tables 3.0 to 3.2, a majority of undergraduate business students in Tamil Nadu leverage Snapchat, Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter for gathering information, enhancing connections with family and friends, as well as forging new friendships. This networking is instrumental in facilitating entrepreneurial aspirations.

Factor Analysis of Entrepreneurial Intention, Its Drivers, and Social Media Use Factors.

Table 4 VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY RESULTS				
Construct	Items	Factor Loading	Total variance explained by construct	Cronbach's α
Entrepreneurial Intention	Starting my own Business sounds attractive to me.	0.962	51.95	0.809
	I would be enthusiastic about running a business.	0.725		
	Have you ever considered founding your own firm?	0.557		
	I would love to run my own business.	0.535		
	Nothing is more exciting than seeing my ideas turn into reality.	0.488		
	I would rather found a new venture than be the manager of an existing one.	0.475		
Perceived Feasibility	It would be very easy to do.	0.727	54.73	0.601
	I am certain that I would be successful.	0.354		
	I know enough to start a business.	0.344		
Perceived Desirability	I would love to be an entrepreneur.	0.869	75.54	0.67
	I trust myself.	0.432		
Usefulness of social media	Using social media will increase my productivity as an entrepreneur.	0.96	63.35	0.853
	Using social media will enhance my effectiveness as an entrepreneur.	0.949		

	Using social media will improve my performance as an entrepreneur.	0.707		
	I will find social media useful in my entrepreneurial activities.	0.598		
	I find it easy to get social media to do what I want it to do.	0.353		
Perceived Privacy & Ease of use	I think privacy policies are effective in social networking sites.	0.477	45.28	0.421
	I think social networking sites are important.	0.48		
	I find social media to be easy to use.	0.41		

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) was performed to examine the construct variables related to entrepreneurial intention, its drivers, and social media usage, along with the structure of the observed measures for five independent variables and additional variables. Using Amos 24, the EFA employed maximum likelihood for estimation. All measurement items were assessed for factor analysis assumptions, including normality, adequate correlations, and the influence of outliers (Hair et al., 1998). The analysis started with a total of 27 items. Three weak items were removed during the EFA, and the analysis ultimately identified seven factors from the remaining 24 items by applying maximum likelihood analysis and the Promax rotation method, based on the criterion of eigenvalues exceeding one.(Table 4).

Examining Student Entrepreneurial Intentions through a Social Media Usage Model via SEM

Several key points must be considered when interpreting the results of our analysis. A significant factor is the role of intention in facilitating and predicting behaviors. Additionally, the model's fit is relevant to both entrepreneurial intention and Social Media engagement. The main aim of this research is to assess a model linking the dependent variable (student entrepreneurial intention) to its predictors (perceived feasibility and perceived desirability); furthermore, it explores how Social Media usage influences both perceived feasibility and desirability. A Structural Equation Model (SEM) is employed for this assessment.

This model aligns with the framework proposed by Shapero and Sokol (1982), examining how perceived feasibility and perceived desirability influence the formation of entrepreneurial

intentions, while also introducing a new variable: "social networking site usage." Many scholars advocate for the utilization of multiple indices to gauge overall model fit (Solymossy, 1998; Tanaka, 1993). Although consensus on the most effective indicator of SEM fit is currently lacking (Hair et al., 1998), the study's results should comply with SEM standards. In this research, we assess the model's fit through various criteria, including the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the normed fit index (NFI), the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), the RMSEA HI 90, and Degrees of Freedom (DF). Those indicators are shown in Table 5, while Figure 2 shows the

	χ^2	df	GFI	RMSEA	RMSEA HI90	NFI	CFI	TLI
Hypothesized Model	556.513	4	0.842	0.428	0.459	0.82	0.82	0.326

Hypothesized model for sample responses with the standardized path estimation. As shown in Table 5, the model offers a good overall fit and is suitable for interpretation. About Hair et al. (1998), all indexes come close to the acceptable range, except for RMSEA and RMSEA HI90. The value of χ^2 is 556.513 with degrees of freedom 4.

Results of Entrepreneurial Intention-Social Media usage model

The SEM path analysis was not run with perceived ease of use and perceived privacy. Once they were excluded, the model was run. The SEM path analysis generates regression weights to test the hypotheses, as shown in Table 6. The effects hypothesized by H1, H2, H3a, H4a, H4b, H4c were significant at $p > 0.001$ level, whereas H3b and H3c were not significant.

Table6
REGRESSIONWEIGHTSFORENTREPRENEURIALINTENTION-SOCIAL
MEDIAUSAGEMODEL

Hypotheses	Relationship		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Supported	
<i>H1</i>	Int	<---	Perceived Desirability	0.547	0.011	50.812	0.001	Yes
<i>H2</i>	Int	<---	Perceived Feasibility	0.668	0.018	37.846	0.001	Yes
<i>H3</i>	Social media	<---	Perceived Desirability	0.554	0.015	50.815	0.001	Yes
<i>H3a</i>	Perceived Ease on social media		Perceived Desirability	0.236	0.049	5.020	0.001	Yes
<i>H3b</i>	Perceived Privacy risk on social media	<---	Perceived Desirability	0.236	0.047	5.046	0.001	Yes
<i>H4</i>	Social media	<---	Perceived Feasibility	0.102	0.063	1.631	0.103	No
<i>H4a</i>	Perceived Ease on social media	<---	Perceived Feasibility	-0.042	0.041	-1.017	0.309	No
<i>H4b</i>	Perceived Privacy risk on social media	<---	Perceived Feasibility	0.133	0.027	4.895	0.001	Yes

Perceived desirability and Perceived feasibility had a significant effect on entrepreneurial intentions. In addition, the perceived competitive usefulness of social media had a significant effect on perceived desirability, and feasibility at $p > 0.001$. However, the perceived feasibility of social media and the perceived feasibility of ease of use, are not significant in explaining variations in desirability ($H4$, $p = 0.103$, and $H4a$, $p = 0.309$, respectively).

Findings:

This research explores the effect of social media usage on students' entrepreneurial intentions. The proposed model offers a framework to comprehend how modern communication technologies and networking shape the aspirations of young entrepreneurs, leveraging the benefits these technologies provide. The results indicate support for hypotheses $H1$, $H2$, $H3$, $H3a$, $H3b$, and $H4b$, while hypotheses $H4$ and $H4a$ do not receive support. This outcome aligns with prior Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) models within the Tamil Nadu region. The notable correlation between perceived desirability, perceived feasibility, and EI not only reinforces findings from the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen (1991) and the model by Krueger et al. (2000) but also confirms these models' validity across varying cultures and environments. Furthermore, these results resonate with studies conducted in other Tamil Nadu universities, such as the work of Aloulou (2016), Ali (2016), Almobaireek and Manolova (2012), and Naushad

(2018), as well as analogous research conducted in Middle Eastern countries like the studies by Al-Bakri and Mehrez (2017) and Hattab (2014). Therefore, the research substantiates the generalizability and relevance of EI models in assessing the entrepreneurial aspirations of students in Tamil Nadu.

Additionally, the findings reveal that social media usage significantly influences students' entrepreneurial intentions through its effect on perceived feasibility. This observation is consistent with previous research on IT adoption, including studies by Mahapatra (2016), Van Slyke et al. (2004), Corritore et al. (2005), Shen (2008), Stern et al. (2008), and Melville et al. (2004). However, it contrasts with earlier works such as Hughes (2016), where of the factors affecting entrepreneurs' decisions to utilize social media, only perceived competitive usefulness notably impacted their intentions, while perceived competitive pressure and trust were not recognized as significant motivators. This suggests that social media indeed promotes and supports entrepreneurial ventures among young entrepreneurs. Therefore, enhancing social media security and internet policies could foster this entrepreneurial intention among student entrepreneurs.

Conclusion:

The results presented hold significant relevance for policymakers and entrepreneurship education. Social media is recognized as a powerful, cost-effective tool for young entrepreneurs to establish new ventures. The data indicate that the intention to engage in entrepreneurship among students is affected by their use of social media and their ability to view these platforms as means to initiate and execute entrepreneurial projects. However, such intentions face limitations due to concerns about trust and competitive dynamics; therefore, this suggests that enhanced security measures, digital literacy programs, and training initiatives would encourage and support entrepreneurial activities among youth.

Limitations and suggestions for Future:

The findings of this study grapple with two paradigms: social media and entrepreneurship. It differs from previous studies in that it tries to establish whether social media and their extreme use influence business students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship as they appreciate its usefulness and importance. However, this area of academic study being relatively new may have some challenges. The data collection of the study based on a sample of undergraduate business students tends to be homogeneous with regard to Social Media use, education, age and entrepreneurship activities. There are indications that some of the dimensions which accompany Gender and Culture may be explained properly. This in turn could be understood as the influence of social media on entrepreneurship intention of students coming from educational backgrounds. However, this also leads to the result that more in depth studies using longitudinal and qualitative methods need to be done on the effect of social media on youth entrepreneurial intention. In note form, it was suggested that a comparison of the effects of social media on the entrepreneurship induction of two cultural groups might be helpful.

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